

Labour Migration in Russia in the Context of Russia's National Security Problem

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Abstract—The article deals with the problems of labour migration in the Russian Federation in the context of Russia's national security, provides the typology of migrants residing in the territory of the Russian Federation and analyzes the risk factors. The author considers the structure of migration flows and the terms of legal, economic and socio-cultural adaptation of migrants in the Russian Federation. In this connection, the status of the Russian migration legislation, the concept of the comprehensive exam in Russian as a foreign language, history of Russia and the basics of the Russian Federation legislation for foreign citizens which was introduced in Russia on January 1, 2015, are analyzed. The article discloses its role as the adaptation strategy and the factor of Russia's migration security.

Keywords—Comprehensive exam, migration policy, migration legislation, Russia's national security.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE modern age is closely connected with the global processes of migration. According to the UN, the total number of migrants in the world is 232 million people, i.e. more than three percent of the world's population [20]. Their distribution is extremely uneven across countries: along with communities quite closed for settling foreign nationals (e.g., Japan) there are states, where the proportion of migrants exceeds half of the number of the employees (e.g., Qatar, Kuwait, the United Arab Emirates) [10]. Among the developed countries the highest share of foreigners in the labour force are in Luxembourg (45%), Australia (24.6%), Switzerland (21.9%), and others [9].

Labour migration is becoming an important issue not only for European countries, but also for Russia, which after the collapse of the Soviet Union has to constantly deal with the a considerable flow of migrants. As a result, the migration processes play a significant role in its socio-economic and demographic development, and directly affect the state of national security of the country. According to the United Nations data for 2015, Russia ranks second in the world (after the US) in the number of migrants. In this regard, at present it is migration security that acquires increasing importance in the formation of the state migration policy of Russia that provides prevention of social conflicts in the area of migration. It acts as a type of security of an individual, society and state. The discourse nature of this phenomenon shows that migration security is linked to the social, economic and cultural areas of life and is supported by the realization of the rights of

individuals and groups, both migrant workers and members of the host community as well as institutionalized state migration policy [1], [3], [4], [17].

Approximating economically developed countries in terms of migration flows, nevertheless while developing migration legislation Russia uses different approaches compared to those of European or American counterparts. Their meaning is as follows: "Working together for the well-being of our countries". At the same time Russia rejects the consumer approach (that is, the obligation of a recipient country to fully provide migrants arriving in the country) [18]. The results of the Russian migration policy in recent years against the migration crisis in Europe show that these approaches in Russia have paid off.

II. STRUCTURE OF MIGRATION FLOWS IN RUSSIA

Now the main group of foreign nationals arriving in the country is labour migrants. The situation is aggravated by the fact that the new generation of workers of the noughties, unlike migrants of the 1990s, have a lower level of education, knowledge of the Russian language and professional skills. While in the early 1990s the main problem of the state in the area of migration was to ensure the rights of forced migrants, in recent decades, due to the changes in the socio-economic situation in the country, the emphasis in the migration policy has objectively shifted to combating illegal migration and its negative consequences. The large number of illegal immigrants (this is currently about 2 million people) in the country remains a major problem in the field of migration, which creates a threat to national security. There are still significant flows of illegal immigration to Russia from the countries with unstable socio-political, economic and sanitary-epidemiological situation. The link between illegal migration, terrorism and organized crime is also becoming obvious to the entire world community.

Russia has become a unique centre of attraction for migrant workers especially among the former Soviet republics. Apart from the areas of employment of migrants (construction, urban transport, housing, work on conveyor belts, etc.), developed back in the 1990s., in the early twenty-first century have been added trade, restaurant business; many migrants are busy providing services to individuals. The growth in the number of foreign migrant workers was taking a particularly active place in the period of the economic growth in the 2000s.

Migration in Russia is caused by various reasons, which are the main catalysts for population movements, inducing people to leave their country and move to other countries. In the case of the former Soviet Union territory one can observe the

action of both "expelling" factors in the countries of the former Soviet Union, and "attractive" factors in Russia, which determines the main directions of migration flows. One of the main expelling factors in this situation is the low rate of economic development in the former Soviet Union countries, which entails high unemployment rate and low wages. The proofs of this are the figures for GDP per capita, shown in Table I [12].

TABLE I
 GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT PER CAPITA IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

Country	GDP per capita (in 2012, in US dollars.)
Russia	17709
Belarus	15634
Kazakhstan	13893
Azerbaijan	10478
Turkmenistan	8718
Ukraine	7374
Georgia	5930
Armenia	5838
Uzbekistan	3555
Kyrgyz Republic	2376
Tajikistan	2229

Long-lasting economic stagnation, and in some cases socio-political instability, recurring aggravation of inter-ethnic tensions in the inter-ethnic area, "playing" the language card lead to an outflow of the population from donor countries and its search for earnings abroad.

In Russia, there is a number of visa and customs barriers with the countries of the former Soviet Union, with which the relations have aggravated in the past few years (for example, for the entry from Georgia into Russia one needs to obtain a visa); however, for the inhabitants of most neighboring countries there remains the easy (visa-free) form to enter the territory of the Russian Federation. Minimum restrictive barriers provide stable flows of labour migration to Russia from these countries. Being a stable socio-political entity with one of the highest standards of living in the post-Soviet territory, close to the culture of the neighboring countries and with relatively weak restrictions on entry, Russia remains an attractive recipient country for the entry of migrants. The combination of these expelling and attractive factors creates a steady flow of labour migration from the former Soviet Union countries to Russia.

For the national security special problems are created by an uncontrolled influx of migrants, which aggravates the social situation, destabilizes the markets of labour and housing, worsens the sanitary-epidemiological situation in the places of migrants' residence; leads to losses in the tax system. Enclavization (i.e. leading a secluded life) of some ethnic communities contributes to the preservation of socio-cultural distance between them and the locals, and the change in the ethnic composition of the territories may, in turn, become threatening and lead to an increase in migrantphobia and conflict on ethnic grounds; 'Ethnic communities will inevitably begin to compete with each other in the areas of

employment, accommodation and communication" [4]. From this point of view, as noted by V.I. Mukomel, migration can be regarded to some extent as a special type of weapons, which can significantly weaken and destabilize the situation in a region or a country as a whole [14] (today the situation in the Middle East and the EU clearly demonstrates this).

By the end of 2015, according to the Federal Migration Service, in the Russian Federation there constantly resided about 9.9 million foreign citizens. However, the number of granted patents on labour activity in 2015 was significantly less than previous year. This is primarily due to the entry of the Republic of Armenia and Kyrgyzstan in 2015 into the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU). The citizens of these two countries may be engaged in labour activities in Russia without obtaining a patent. At the same time the state constantly monitors violations of legislative and other normative legal acts of the Russian Federation. As a result, for 12 months of 2015 an administrative action was brought against more than 2 million 225 thousand migrants. There were imposed fines for 8 billion 753 million 081 thousand roubles. Over 117 thousand migrants were expelled and deported. (In 2014 - over 139 thousand). The entry for more than 481 thousand foreigners was closed (it can be denied for the violation of the period of stay in the Russian Federation, unauthorized departure from special centres for migrants, crimes). There was closed the entry for more than 481 thousand foreigners (the entry can be denied for the violation of the period of stay in the Russian Federation, unauthorized departure from special centres for migrants, crimes). Although the proportion of offenses committed by foreigners, according to the head of the Federal Migration Service of Russia K. Romodanovsky does not exceed 3.8% of the all crimes [7].

The main donors of labour resources, until recently were the countries of Central Asia, namely - Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan [13]. Despite the declining incomes, which are clearly demonstrated by almost twofold reduction in remittances from migrant workers to their homeland from Russia, the Russian labour market remains the only option for the majority of employees from the Central Asian countries. Just a reminder: according to the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, in the first quarter of 2015 \$ 1.781 billion was sent by money transfer systems to the CIS countries, which is 47 percent less than in the first quarter of 2014 (\$ 3.364 billion). Compared with the first quarter of 2014, the volume of remittances to Uzbekistan decreased by 49 percent, to Tajikistan - by 44 percent, to Kyrgyzstan - by 41 percent, to Kazakhstan - by 39 per cent, to Turkmenistan - by 57 percent.

If we compare the figures for the period under review with the fourth quarter of 2014, the drop of volumes is even more impressive: Uzbekistan fell short of 53 percent, Tajikistan - 55.5 per cent, Kyrgyzstan - 49.5 percent, Kazakhstan - 46.7 percent and Turkmenistan - 85, 7 percent [8].

In 2015, as compared to 2014, the Federal Migration Service of Russia recorded a sharp decline in the number of migrants entering the country - almost 70% of the number of entries and departures of foreign nationals.

According to the head of the Federal Migration Service, the number of citizens of the Central Asian countries in Russia, except Kyrgyzstan, is decreasing, whereas at the same time the number of citizens of Moldova and Ukraine is increasing. Thus, at present in Russia there are about 2,5 million Ukrainian citizens, 1.1 million of them come from the south-east of Ukraine. "There is a kind of substitution", - Romodanovsky remarked, adding that the number of migrants from China, South Korea and the DPRK is also increasing.

Approximating economically developed countries in terms of migration flows, nevertheless while developing migration legislation Russia uses different approaches compared to those of European or American counterparts. Their meaning is as follows: "working together for the well-being of our countries". At the same time Russia rejects the consumer approach (i.e. the obligation of a recipient country to fully provide migrants arriving in the country). The results of the Russian migration policy in recent years against the migration crisis in Europe show that these approaches in Russia have paid off [2].

III. CHANGES IN THE MIGRATION LEGISLATION OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

In the today's Russian society, with an increase in the scale and expansion of international migration geography there is a pressing issue of the regulation and the quota system of the volume of labour migration and reasonable use of the potential of foreign labour force. In order to ensure national security, to maintain the optimal balance of labour resources, to promote the priority employment of Russian citizens, as well as to solve other problems of internal and foreign policy of the state, the Russian government has the right to set quotas for foreign citizens arriving in Russia in the way not requiring a visa, work permit in the territory of Russia and its separate regions. Migration registration of foreign citizens and stateless people residing and working permanently or temporarily in the territory of the Russian Federation is the main form of regulating migration processes in our country [19].

In 2015 there were adopted a number of laws that change foreigners' order of stay in the Russian Federation. From January 1, 2015 the CIS citizens are to enter the territory of Russia by foreign passports. The exception to the rule are citizens of the member-states of the Customs Union and the Single Economic Area (Belarus and Kazakhstan).

From 2010 in Russia there was the Patent employment system for migrants coming to Russia from countries with visa-free regime. Initially, a foreigner could acquire a patent for the employment for citizens of the Russian Federation, who hired a foreign national for the job, not related to entrepreneurial activity. Since January 1, 2015 the patent system has been introduced for all categories of labour migrants from visa-free countries. In accordance with the document a patent is granted for one month with the possibility of extension up to a year. One can get it within 30 days from the date of entry into Russia.

One has to obtain a patent, if a citizen remarked a job as the purpose of the visit in the migration card when crossing the

Russian border. It is legal entities and private entrepreneurs who can hire foreign labour force on the basis of a patent. Besides, for the first time there have been legally registered grounds on which a patent may be revoked or denied. They include various offenses, bringing to justice repeatedly, a number of infectious diseases, etc. In order to obtain such a document, one is to pass a medical examination, pass exams, get a TIN (Tax Identification Number) and health insurance. One is to do all this within 30 days from the date of the entry into the country. It is the employers who are to have their share in the payment for all these procedures, if they are really interested in an employee. Punishment for the use of illegal labour force will be toughened. Illegal migrants violating the migration regime for a long time will be denied by the entry into the Russian Federation for a period of 10 years.

The territory of the effect of a patent is limited to the region where it is obtained, and the regions themselves have the right to set the price for it (personal income tax - PIT). Due to the cancellation of the work permit and change of labour patents scheme, the taxation of each foreign employee will be comparable to a citizen of Russia - 13% personal income tax. Employers will continue to pay insurance premiums for their employees. It is also planned to issue sick leaves to migrants. Employers will be obliged to pay fees to the social insurance fund in the amount of 1.8% of a foreign employee's salary. In order to obtain benefits, one is to pay insurance premiums for six months preceding the month in which the insurance event occurs, that is, a foreigner is to work in the company for at least six months.

On June 1, 2015 a ban on working in Russia for drivers with a foreign driver's license was introduced ; all foreign drivers of commercial vehicles (taxi drivers, buses, etc.) will need to have the Russian-style driver's license. One can still drive a private car with a foreign driver's license.

IV. PROBLEMS OF MIGRANTS' ADAPTATION

It should be borne in mind that the very link between migration and security is bilateral: it is not only security of society and state, affected by migration processes, but also safety of migrants themselves, which largely depends on the type of movement (migration) and its grounds. In this regard, an important task of the state migration policy of the Russian Federation is to create conditions for migrants' adaptation and integration, to provide them with legal and social protection, which involves the development of state programs of adaptation and integration in order to overcome migrants' isolation from the host society and provide national security of the country [18].

From December 1, 2012, in the Russian Federation there was a law introducing a compulsory exam in the Russian language for those migrants who work in the areas of housing and communal services, trade and social services. On January 1, 2015 according to the presidential decree of May 7, 2012 № 602 "Concerning the Promotion of Interethnic Concord" [16] there came into force the Federal Law "On Amendments to the Federal Law "On the Legal Status of Foreign Citizens in the Russian Federation", according to which when obtaining a

work permit, temporary residence and residence permit foreign citizens are to prove not only the level of proficiency in Russian, but also knowledge of history of Russia and the basics of Russian legislation [15]. The initiators of the development of the examination concept were the Ministry of Education and the Federal Migration Service (FMS), which intend, among other things, to reduce the flow of low-skilled labour force, to improve migrants' educational level and at the same time to increase revenue. On December 30, 2015 there was adopted the Federal law of the Russian Federation № 465-FZ "On Amendments to Article 15.1 of the Federal law "On the legal status of foreign citizens in the Russian Federation", according to which citizens of Belarus are exempt from taking the comprehensive exam [6]. Thus, for foreigners' successful socio-cultural adaptation and their socialization there is a set of the tasks of implementing educational programs in the following areas – the Russian language, Russian history and the basics of the legislation of the Russian Federation. Citizens wishing to find a job in Russia, along with the Russian language and the basics of the Russian Federation legislation, must master the material on Russian history to the extent necessary for a temporary stay in the territory of the Russian Federation in order to be engaged in the labour activities [11]. This area in the concept of migration policy of modern Russia is of great importance because the presence of a significant number of foreigners in the society who are not able to fully adapt to the cultural and social conditions of the host country, provokes tension in the society and poses a potential threat to inter-ethnic concord. This, in turn, may have an impact on the state of the national security of the host country. At the same time the Russian authorities take into account the fact that the adaptive potential of labour migrants in Russia is limited, their educational motivation remains rather low, since migrants of new generations coming to the Russian Federation from the CIS countries have a low level of the knowledge of the Russian language and professional skills. Therefore, the Ministry of Education of Russia set the task not only to formulate the requirements for knowledge of the language, history and laws, but also to develop a program of assistance to migrants in mastering these disciplines. In this regard, adaptation and integration events include a set of services provided to migrants by public and local authorities, aimed at teaching the Russian language, Russian history and the basics of the Russian legislation. Foreigners who have passed the exam will be issued a special certificate, valid for five years [5].

In accordance with the 357 Federal Law the Russian Federation subjects also have the right to develop their own procedures for the comprehensive examination. As of January 1, 2016, 46 Russian Federation subjects started the normative development of the comprehensive exam.

By December 30, 2015 the total number of foreign citizens who had passed the comprehensive exam was 1 million people, out of which 693,521 people passed the exam at the level of "foreign worker"; 123, 353 people - at the level of "temporary residence"; 57,055 people - at the level of "residence permit". Just a few months after the start of the

comprehensive exam in Russia it became obvious that a significant part of this category of foreign citizens successfully copes with the control materials of the tests (as evidenced by Fig. 1) and obtains a certificate.

In all, in 2015 citizens of 148 countries of the world passed the comprehensive exam. In 2015 the comprehensive exam was passed by more than 2 million foreign citizens and stateless people: by the federal procedure - 1 million 790 thousand foreign citizens; by the regional procedure - 450 thousand people.

Fig. 2 shows the statistics of those who passed the comprehensive examination in the context of the countries of the migration exodus in 2015. It is evident that the largest number of those who passed the exam are citizens of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Ukraine.

Fig. 1 Statistics of the success rate of passing the comprehensive exam

Fig. 2 Statistics of foreign citizens who passed the comprehensive exam

The analysis of the first results of the comprehensive examination led to the conclusion that, firstly, in Russia there have increased the requirements for migrants, and this, in turn, leads to qualitative changes in migration flows. According to experts, 10 to 20% of migrants with poor results of the comprehensive examination are forced to leave the territory of Russia. Secondly, migrants themselves are aware of the need to study the Russian language, Russian history and the basics

of the Russian legislation in order to stay in the country comfortably.

Thirdly, the introduction of the mandatory comprehensive exam has formed "multiplier effect." The leaders of the former Soviet republics at the moment are seriously concerned that a part of the population can't find jobs in the territory of Russia, and this, in turn, will lead to economic crisis in these countries and aggravated social situation due to the increase in unemployment rate. At the moment in such countries as Uzbekistan and Tajikistan there was launched a campaign for the resumption of activities of Russian schools, as well as the organization of pre-migration training.

V. CONCLUSION

On the whole, it can be said that the migration processes in Russia occur in about the same way as in many developed countries. Both Russia and the Western countries have common problems related to labour migration, namely illegal labour migration and the formation of national communities that impede the processes of integration of foreign citizens in recipient countries.

For the Russian society, the priority of which is to preserve its statehood, the development of effective migration policy is among the most important conditions of achieving economic and political integration, sustainable development and national security. In order to ensure the national security of the state, the migration policy of the Russian Federation is aimed at providing a balance between economic, social and political interests of the host population and migrants, taking into consideration their ethnic, linguistic, cultural and religious differences and peculiarities.

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